

MEASURING THE IMPACT OF ETHNOCENTRISM ON INDIAN YOUTH-AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON KHADI FABRIC CHOICE OF PREFERENCE

**D.M. Arvind Mallik, PES Institute of Technology and Management,
India**

**Keerthan Raj, Shri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara Institute for
Management Development, India**

**Arthur Fernandes, Kirloskar Institute of Advanced Management
Studies, India**

**Amith Donald Menezes, Mangalore Institute of Technology &
Engineering, India**

ABSTRACT

Background: Khadi, a traditional handspun fabric, represents India's self-reliance and eco-friendliness. With changing fashion trends, this study explores how Indian youth perceive Khadi in terms of sustainability, fashion and cultural significance. **Objectives:** The study aims to analyze young consumers' attitudes towards Khadi, focusing on its eco-friendliness, cost and fashion appeal, while identifying key factors influencing their purchasing decisions. **Methodology:** A descriptive research approach was used, collecting survey data from 120 youth respondents. The analysis focused on perceptions related to fabric preference, pricing and brand loyalty. **Findings:** Results show that most respondents consider Khadi eco-friendly and culturally significant, with women displaying a higher preference for Khadi due to its design variety. However, pricing remains a concern. **Results:** Younger consumers, especially women, have a positive attitude towards Khadi, driven by its eco-friendliness and cultural significance. However, there is a need for more fashionable and affordable options to expand its appeal further. **Discussion:** Promoting Khadi supports sustainable fashion and traditional artisans, contributing to cultural preservation and environmental sustainability. **Conclusion:** This study offers insights into how youth view Khadi and suggests ways to enhance its market appeal through affordability and modern design.

Keywords: Khadi, Youth Perception, Sustainable Fashion, Cultural Value, Consumer Behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Ethnocentrism, the belief in the superiority of one's own culture, is of particular importance to consumer behaviour and brand preferences of youth. Datta, D. B. and Sarkar, B. (2022) believe that marketers who are interested in connecting with young consumers in a country rich in cultural diversity and heritage need to understand impact of ethnocentrism. As globalization influences consumer landscapes, young Indians are beginning to express their cultural identity in their purchase selections. The study also shows that customers are willing to shop at local businesses that are closer to their core cultural beliefs and they prefer domestic goods such as Khadi. Secondly, it is hoped that in this thesis, light will be thrown on how cultural identity and nationalistic sentiment affect purchase decisions in today's highly

globalized mass-market economy through the study of the relationship between ethnocentrism and choice about Khadi.

Although the Indian youth have been increasingly exposed to global brands and international marketing, but their purchasing decisions are predominantly influenced by deep-rooted cultural identities and nationalistic feelings. In his study on Khadi-a traditional Indian fabric-known for its principles of self-reliance and sustainability as well as serving as a symbol of national pride-Ghoshal T emphasizes on these elements of Khadi. Consumer preferences among young Indians will be shaped, at least to some extent, by Khadi's historical significance in India's struggle for independence (Aronczyk, M. (2013). With globalization becoming ever more omnipresent in all aspects of our lives, the interplay between ethnocentrism and brand preference becomes more important. Even if you are a young consumer, you tend to show a preference for domestic products to represent your cultural identity and support local artisans. The 'sense of loyalty and pride in one's heritage' also can be attributed to ethnocentric attitude, this inclination towards indigenous brands can be due to such kind of inclination towards indigenous brands.

Additionally, ethnocentrism can result in the rejection towards foreign products that are considered threats to local culture and economy, as previously displayed specifically in the Indian context as historical contexts and socio-political factors in play, which complicates the relationship that currently exists between local and global brands, in their study they wish to understand how ethnocentrism works. This research examines the link between ethnocentrism and consumer selections on the purchase of Khadi, so as to contribute to the knowledge of how cultural identity is elaborated through purchase decisions. For firms in India fast-changing market, it is important to understand these dynamics. To begin with, this study has important practical implications for marketers as it helps to navigate the complex terrain of the Indian customers' preferences in an era of globalization; and also contributes to knowledge in consumer behaviour. This empirical study examines how ethnocentric attitudes affect brand preference among Indian youth, by analyzing a traditional Indian fabric symbolizing pride in their country and independence, Khadi.

Ethnocentrism-Meaning

As explained by Bizumic, B. (2020), ethnocentrism has a major role on the behaviour and brand preferences of consumers, especially among youth. Additionally, Ding, Q. S. states that ethnocentrism (which is the belief that one's own culture is superior to any other) influences in a significant way feelings of patriotism and adherence to traditional customs and especially applies to the influence of the consumption preferences on the distinctive characteristics of the product variety that is considered as pretentious. As a nation with as culturally diverse as India, where several traditions and values mingle, the extent to which ethnocentrism affects young consumers is wide ranging and profound. Marketers and policymakers interested in engaging with the youth demographic, a proportionally important part of the consumer market, should understand this phenomenon.

Overview of India's Textile Sector: A Historical and Economic Perspective

India's textile sector is one of the oldest industries in the country, with a rich history spanning centuries. Misra, S. informs today, it remains a vital contributor to the economy, accounting for approximately 13% of total exports. The industry is divided into two main segments: The unorganized sector, which includes handloom and handicrafts produced on a small scale using traditional methods and the organized sector, which utilizes modern machinery for spinning, weaving and garment production. From hand-spun fabrics to large-scale manufacturing, the Indian textile industry exhibits diversity. This is a sector with the close bond of agriculture, especially the raw materials like cotton and inherited from the Indian cultural heritage. The Indian textile industry continues to play a very significant role in the global economy as a significant player in the global textile economy, capable of producing a large range of high-

quality and affordable textiles both for domestic markets and international markets.

Consumer perception and behavior towards sustainable products specifically with traditional fabrics like Khadi has been studied. India's National fabric, referred to as Khadi, historically and also culturally carries great significance in India; especially closely associated with the Swadeshi movement of Mahatma Gandhi. Others have talked about how Khadi's symbolism of self-sufficiency and national pride has affected older generations. There is however very little research on how younger generations of a rapidly globalizing India perceive Khadi about modern fashion and sustainability (Alam, A. S; Goenka, A; Nandkeolyar, D., 2022).

It has been recently reported in the literature that the awareness of environmental issues has enhanced consumer preference for eco-friendly and ethically produced goods mainly among youth. This is why Khadi, an eco-friendly and sustainable fabric, has a natural edge over this. Studies, however, found that even though Khadi is environmentally friendly, it has small market share as a result of being tied to traditional or dated fashion. As traditionally perceived by youth consumers, Khadi is a fabric more appropriate for the generation that is older and therefore it is not considered as mainstream fashion. Another important thing affecting the market penetration of Khadi is the sensitivity of price. Jain, P. research found that while young consumers tend to pay a premium on eco-friendly products, Khadi products are also perceived as expensive; and far more than fast fashion. These studies equip the Khadi producers to align their product range with the taste of the contemporary fashion trends as well as priced and stylish goods that can attract the young consumers.

Ethnocentrism

Ethnocentrism significantly influences various societal elements, including patriotism, collectivism, animosity, dogmatism and both the political and economic environments. In the context of patriotism, individuals often express pride in their national identity and cultural heritage, which can foster a preference for domestic products as symbols of national pride. Bizumic, B. (2014) emphasises collectivism emphasizes group cohesion and shared goals, leading to loyalty towards one's cultural group while potentially marginalizing outsiders (Bar-Tal, D., 1990). This can result in animosity towards foreign cultures or products perceived as threats to national identity. Additionally, ethnocentrism can breed dogmatism, where individuals rigidly adhere to their beliefs without considering alternative perspectives, hindering intercultural dialogue. Politically, ethnocentric sentiments can shape policies that prioritize national interests over global cooperation, impacting international relations (Bizumic, B., & Duckitt, J. 2012). Economically, strong ethnocentric tendencies encourage consumers to favour local goods over foreign ones, as seen in India's promotion of Khadi as a symbol of self-reliance and national pride. Together, these elements illustrate the complex interplay between ethnocentrism and various aspects of society.

Factors Responsible for Ethnocentrism

Patriotism: A person's emotional connection to their nation is referred to as patriotism and it is frequently characterised by pride in its identity and cultural legacy. Both sentimental and practical aspects of this attachment are present: Sentimental patriotism displays strong emotional attachments to the country's identity, whilst practical patriotism is connected to the material advantages of citizenship. Ethnocentrism and patriotism sometimes collide in India, encouraging a preference for indigenous products and customs as displays of pride and allegiance to the country. Consumer perception and behaviour towards sustainable products specifically with traditional fabrics like Khadi has been studied. India's National Fabric, referred to as Khadi, historically and culturally carries great significance in India; especially closely associated with the Swadeshi movement of Mahatma Gandhi. Others have talked about how Khadi's symbolism of self-sufficiency and national pride has affected older generations.

Animosity: Hostility or animosity, as a tendency to respond with hostility or resentment towards other groups, can have great effect on consumer behaviour as well as social dynamics. Klein and Ettensoe note that ethnocentrism can increase animosity by creating negative stereotypes and distorted perceptions of out groups. In India, this looks like consumer preference, with local products preferred over foreign alternatives because they feel that they contribute to a threat to national identity and cultural integrity. Finally, such sentiments can easily generate a form of economic nationalism, where local consumers are encouraged to spend their money on habit and pride associated with their cultural heritage. However, this also perpetuates animosity which, in turn, stifles healthy competition, with the acceptance of foreign brands that would otherwise help make the market healthier. However, while ethnocentric to some extent underscores local economic growth, too much animosity against foreign entities serves to obstruct globalization and cross-cultural exchange, jeopardizing opportunities for sharing and innovation in a rapidly interlocked world. Addressing the underlying problems should help stakeholders in working towards the creation of an environment which does not shy away from diversity but appreciates local products and which removes the negative impact of animosity and ethnocentrism of the consumers.

Collectivism: Collectivism fosters loyalty and a sense of solidarity within cultural communities by prioritising the cohesiveness and common objectives of the group over individual interests. This orientation promotes putting the welfare of the group first in highly collectivist countries like India, which frequently leads to ethnocentrism, in which members have a strong sense of loyalty to their own cultural group, sometimes at the detriment of others. As people align their behaviours with the interests of their community rather than their own objectives, ethnocentric tendencies become more noticeable, often marginalising outsiders while also promoting group togetherness. There is however very little research on how younger generations of a rapidly globalizing India perceive Khadi in relation to modern fashion and sustainability.

Economic Environment: In the economic context, ethnocentrism influences consumer behavior by encouraging preferences for local products over foreign ones. Strong ethnocentric tendencies can lead to the belief that purchasing domestic goods supports the national economy and local employment. This sentiment is particularly relevant in India, where Khadi and other indigenous products are promoted as symbols of self-reliance and national pride. These elements illustrate how ethnocentrism interacts with various aspects of society, influencing attitudes and behaviors across patriotism, collectivism, animosity, dogmatism, political dynamics and economic choices. It has been recently reported in the literature that the awareness of environmental issues has enhanced consumer preference for eco-friendly and ethically produced goods mainly among youth. This is why Khadi, an eco-friendly and sustainable fabric, has a natural edge over this. Studies, however, found that even though Khadi is environmentally friendly, it has small market share because of being tied to traditional or dated fashion. As traditionally perceived by youth consumers, Khadi is a fabric more appropriate for the older generation and therefore it is not considered as mainstream fashion. Another important thing affecting the market penetration of Khadi is the sensitivity of price. Jain, P. research found that while young consumers tend to pay a premium on eco-friendly products, Khadi products are also perceived as expensive and far more than fast fashion. These studies equip the Khadi producers to align their product range with the taste of the contemporary fashion trends as well as priced and stylish goods that can attract the young consumers.

Role of Ethnocentrism in Consumer Behavior

Ethnocentrism is the demonstration of the need to decide another culture based on postulates found in the qualities and norms of one's way of life. Ethnocentric behaviour involves judging different gatherings about the prejudices of one's ethnic grouping or culture, particularly concerning language, behaviour, traditions and religion. These angles or classifications are qualifications that characterize each ethnic personality. Organizations are facing stiff competition due to globalization, at the same time investment in foreign markets is increasing significantly.

Karoui, S., & Khemakhem, R., recently, owing to the technical and communication developments global marketing activities have increased astonishingly consumers' bias towards their national products is a significant determinant of local product purchase behavior. By exploring the attitudes of consumers towards domestic and foreign products, local and global marketers can take significant inputs to formulate more effective marketing strategies. The increased consumer awareness of foreign cultures, global markets and foreign brands has increased the importance of studies that explore consumer ethnocentric tendencies. In this context, thorough study of consumer ethnocentrism will enable marketers to undergo effective marketing strategies to penetrate the global markets. Organizations need to have extensive knowledge of consumer ethnocentricity before internationalizing their ventures.

India's deep connection to its cultural roots is exemplified through Khadi, a hand-woven fabric that symbolizes national identity and self-reliance. Trivedi, L. N., says in the early 20th century, Mahatma Gandhi played a pivotal role in promoting Khadi as a means for economic empowerment and independence from British textiles. He argued that factory owners often denied handloom weavers access to affordable yarn, which perpetuated poverty among artisans. Joshi, D., interprets Gandhi encouraged Indians to spin their cotton using the charkha (spinning wheel), making it a symbol of the nationalist movement. He urged members of the Indian National Congress to engage in spinning as a form of contribution to the cause. This grassroots movement aimed to revive local economies by fostering self-sufficiency and unity among diverse communities. Khadi became more than just a fabric; it represented a collective effort to reclaim economic independence and dignity for the masses. Shah, N., concludes that by promoting Khadi, Gandhi sought to bridge social divides and empower rural artisans, ultimately transforming it into a powerful emblem of India's struggle for freedom and self-reliance.

Conceptual Background

The conceptual framework for this study is rooted in understanding how ethnocentrism, sustainability and fashion consciousness influence consumer behavior, specifically regarding Khadi. Ethnocentrism, the belief in the superiority of one's own ethnic products, plays a significant role in shaping purchasing decisions. Khadi, as a symbol of Indian heritage, appeals to ethnocentric consumers who prefer domestic over foreign goods. This concept is especially relevant when examining youth attitudes toward Khadi, as national pride can be a driver for choosing products that are "Made in India". Sustainability has become a crucial factor in consumer decision-making, especially among the younger generation. Sustainable fashion, which emphasizes eco-friendly production methods and the ethical sourcing of materials, is gaining prominence. Bawa, A. (2004) explain Khadi, produced without harmful chemicals and supporting local artisans, aligns well with this movement. However, the challenge lies in overcoming perceptions that Khadi is outdated or unsuitable for contemporary fashion needs (Carpenter, J. M., Moore, M., Alexander, N., & Doherty, A. M. 2013). Finally, fashion consciousness-defined as the level of concern an individual has regarding their appearance and how fashionable they are perceived to be-affects consumer preferences (Ranjbarian, B., Barari, M., & Zabihzade, K. 2011). Khadi's association with traditional wear limits its appeal to fashion-conscious youth who seek trendy, stylish clothing options. This study aims to explore how these three factors-ethnocentrism, sustainability and fashion consciousness-affect youth perceptions of Khadi.

Conceptual Framework for Ethnocentrism in Indian Culture

Ethnocentrism, the belief that one's own culture is superior to others, significantly influences various aspects of society, including patriotism, collectivism, animosity, dogmatism and the political and economic environments, below is a detailed exploration of how these elements interact with the concept of ethnocentrism in the context of Indian culture Figure 1.

FIGURE 1
RESEARCHER CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK ON CONSUMER ETHNOCENTRISM

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Statement of the Problem

Ethnocentrism is the demonstration that a decision must be made about another culture, based on predispositions found in the qualities and criteria of one's own way of life. Ethnocentric behavior includes the judgment of different gatherings for the predispositions of one's own ethnic grouping or culture, particularly concerning language, behavior, traditions and religion. In addition, product notices are almost always published in all media, such as print, web, radio, television and entry. While choosing the right item, customers should pay more attention to the value, quality, benefits and reliability of the item. To distinguish the client's inclination towards Khadi, We chose this subject in our exploration in understanding how today's youth view Khadi as a product or brand or way of life.

Scope of the Study

The purpose of this survey is to learn more about the buying habits and habits of young people in Shivamogga with relation to Khadi products. For Charkha and Khadi Bhandars, which concentrate on Khadi clothing, the results will be especially helpful. Producers can create goods and services that draw in new clients while keeping existing ones with customized offerings by looking at these consumer trends to gain a deeper understanding of the tastes and inclinations of youthful consumers (Bhattacharyya, 2011). By better-matching products to the tastes of young people, this focused strategy might help convert non-users into Khadi customers.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the youth brand preference towards Khadi.
- To understand the youth's various attributes while buying Khadi products.

- To study the impact of antecedents and consequences of consumer ethnocentrism different elements.

Research Methodology

The purpose of this analysis is to explore the impact of consumer ethnocentrism on the different stages of consumer making decision process across the product categories of domestic origin. The specific goal of the study is to examine the potential interrelations between researched concepts based on theoretical assumption and past research. The research design for this study is descriptive, utilizing a non-probability sampling method to collect data. The sampling techniques employed include convenience sampling and quota sampling, with a gender balance of 50% male and 50% female respondents. The study focuses on the youth population in Shivamogga city, specifically targeting individuals aged 18 to 27, with an equal gender representation. A structured questionnaire serves as the primary data collection instrument. Given the infinite population context, a sample size of 100 was selected, aligning with a calculated sample of 96 respondents based on a 10% margin of error, a 95% confidence level and a 50% response distribution.

Sources of Data

Primary Data: The primary data of this study is information collected from primary sources that is through focus groups, surveys, interview and questionnaire. The questionnaire is an important source used in this study.

Secondary Data: The secondary data of this study is quantitative data which is collected from journals, company websites, marketing textbooks and company annual progress reports.

Data Analysis

Table 1 reflects the trend of the youth going in for the Khadi dress, which seems to be catching on well, for it resonates well with the youth. 67% of respondents believe that the Khadi dress trend has the potential to attract young consumers, while 33% disagree. The sentiment toward Khadi is positive and augurs a growing consciousness of its environmental and cultural value, as well as its stylishness. If young people become aware of sustainability, the trend of Khadi interest will further rise owing to global trends for ethical and sustainable fashion. With the younger demographic becoming more and more conscious in the decisions they make with consumer purchasing, the appeal of Khadi, a tradition rooted in tradition yet modernized enough to fit into today's aesthetics, could be a favorite choice. Bansal and Kaur claim that this trend enhances return to cultural roots as well as the Khadi is a fashionable and socially responsible option that is relevant in today's environment (Bansal & Kaur, 2019). This momentum can be used to draw in brands to overcome the challenge of reaching youth and create a customer base that takes style and sustainability seriously Table 1.

Question	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
Is Khadi cloth eco-friendly?			
Strongly agree	31	31	A significant majority (63%) believe Khadi cloth is eco-friendly due to its natural production methods that avoid harmful chemicals
Agree	63	63	
Neutral	3	3	
Disagree	3	3	
Strongly disagree	0	0	
Total	1000	100%	

How do you compare the price of Khadi?			
Cheap	8	8	Nearly half (48%) of respondents find the price of Khadi reasonable, attributing this to domestic production which reduces import duties
Reasonable	48	48	
Costly	42	42	
Very costly	2	2	
Total	1000	100%	
Do you prefer Khadi?			
Cotton	50	50	Half of the respondents prefer cotton Khadi for its comfort and suitability across seasons
Silk	29	29	
Polyester	13	13	
Woolen	8	8	
Total	1000	100%	
Which brand of cloth line do you prefer in Khadi?			
Raymond's	30	30	The Desi outlet is the most preferred brand (35%), known for its strong association with Khadi in Shivamogga
Reid and Taylor	22	22	
Desi	35	35	
Khadi from handloom	13	13	
Total	1000	100%	
In which season do you use Khadi cloth?			
In winter	11	11	A majority (57%) prefer wearing Khadi in summer, appreciating its coolness during hot weather
In summer	57	57	
In rainy	22	22	
In all seasons	10	10	
Total	1000	100%	
Whom do you think Khadi cloths will be used more by			
Male	44	44	Female respondents (56%) are using Khadi cloth compared to men because Khadi has more variety and designs than men who chose for themselves
Female	56	56	
Do you think foreigners are buying our Khadi product?			
Strongly agree	16	16	67 (67%) of respondents agree that Foreigners are willing to buy our Khadi product because Khadi is the cloth most liked by foreigners and they also respect the Khadi
Agree	67	67	
Neutral	12	12	
Disagree	4	4	
Strongly disagree	1	1	

State the Various Factors that Influenced to Buy Khadi Cloth

From the Table 2, it observed that wearing Khadi does acknowledge patriotism which is followed by quality in weaving will be superior as the price is reasonable at lastly, Color referees are those factors that will influence youth to buy Khadi Table 2.

Particular	1	2	3	4	Mean	Rank
Color preference	26	23	38	13	2.38	4
Quality is superior to wear	10	43	20	27	2.64	2
Price is reasonable	18	27	40	15	2.52	3
Pride of our nation	14	25	24	37	2.84	1

Do you Believe the Trend of Khadi Dress will Satisfy to Attract Consumers, Especially Youth?

67 (67%) of respondents believe the trend of Khadi dress will satisfy and has potential to attract especially youth Table 3 and 4.

Particular	No of respondents	%
Yes	67	67
No	33	33
Total	1000	1000

Particular	1	2	3	4	Mean	Rank
Quality is questionable	8	7	14	4	2.8	3
Price is not modest	6	14	6	7	2.82	2
It's not trend	5	12	7	9	2.86	1
Not interested to wear	13	5	4	11	2.79	4

From the above graph it observed that at available time, Khadi is not a trend to wear, price is not modest as quality would be bottleneck and at last, youths weren't may be not interested to wear Table 5-7.

Particular	1	2	3	4	Mean	Rank
Add more colors/variety	33	19	22	26	2.41	5
Enhance new designs patterns	21	26	26	27	2.59	3
Must be fashionable according to trend	16	32	24	28	2.64	2
Embroidery work on cloth	19	28	34	19	2.53	4
Make Khadi as brand than cloth	13	27	35	25	2.72	1

Element	Definition	Link to ethnocentrism
Patriotism	Strong emotional attachment to India and its heritage	Enhances patriotic feelings, fostering the belief in the superiority of Indian culture and rejecting foreign influences

Collectivism	Emphasis on group harmony and familial bonds	Reinforces group identity, promoting the idea that collective norms are superior, potentially excluding outsiders
Animosity	Hostility towards other groups	Increases animosity by fostering negative stereotypes and perceptions of other cultures, leading to regional or religious tensions
Dogmatism	Rigid adherence to beliefs without considering alternatives	Promotes dogmatism, causing individuals to dismiss other cultural practices as inferior, hindering understanding and dialogue
Political environment	Diverse political ideologies in India	Shapes political discourse, leading to policies favoring certain cultural groups while marginalizing others
Economic environment	A mix of traditional and modern economic practices	Drives consumers to prefer local products over foreign ones, impacting trade policies and reinforcing nationalistic sentiments

Table 7
THE SURVEY QUESTIONS ON KHADI AND OTHER CULTURAL ELEMENTS

Parameter	Questions	Particular	No. of respondents	%	Z-Test	Mean	Mode	Standard Deviation (SD)	Variance																																																																																	
Pride in Indian culture	Do you have respect or pride about our Indian culture?	Yes	80	80	6.32	50	Yes	30.98	960																																																																																	
		No	20	20						Patriotism	A real Indian should always buy Indian-made products	Strongly agree	30	30	2.02	40.4	Agree	20.07	402.8	Agree	53	53	Neutral	11	11	Disagree	2	2	Strongly disagree	4	4	Collectivism	Do you have a fashion for collecting traditional or modern dress?	Traditional	62	62	2.97	50	Traditi-onal	17	289	Modern	38	38	Animosity	Do you have animosity towards foreign brands?	Strongly agree	24	24	1.08	25	Agree	16.37	267.84	Agree	49	49	Neutral	18	18	Disagree	5	5	Strongly disagree	4	4	Dogmatism	Should the government take care of Khadi production?	Agree	74	74	5.89	50	Agree	24	576	Disagree	26	26	Do you think the government should make Khadi proud?	Strongly agree	19	19	0.97	32	Agree	16.54	273.86	Agree	51
Patriotism	A real Indian should always buy Indian-made products	Strongly agree	30	30	2.02	40.4	Agree	20.07	402.8																																																																																	
		Agree	53	53																																																																																						
		Neutral	11	11																																																																																						
		Disagree	2	2																																																																																						
		Strongly disagree	4	4																																																																																						
Collectivism	Do you have a fashion for collecting traditional or modern dress?	Traditional	62	62	2.97	50	Traditi-onal	17	289																																																																																	
		Modern	38	38																																																																																						
Animosity	Do you have animosity towards foreign brands?	Strongly agree	24	24	1.08	25	Agree	16.37	267.84																																																																																	
		Agree	49	49																																																																																						
		Neutral	18	18																																																																																						
		Disagree	5	5																																																																																						
		Strongly disagree	4	4																																																																																						
Dogmatism	Should the government take care of Khadi production?	Agree	74	74	5.89	50	Agree	24	576																																																																																	
		Disagree	26	26																																																																																						
	Do you think the government should make Khadi proud?	Strongly agree	19	19	0.97	32	Agree	16.54	273.86																																																																																	
		Agree	51	51																																																																																						
		Neutral	10	10																																																																																						
Disagree	14	14																																																																																								

		Strongly disagree	6	6					
Political environment	Should Khadi be made compulsory for all government employees?	Strongly agree	21	21	1.13	20	Agree	14.18	201.16
		Agree	46	46					
		Neutral	13	13					
		Disagree	11	11					
		Strongly disagree	9	9					
	Should politicians wear Khadi?	Agree	78	78	5.7	50	Agree	28	784
Disagree	22	22							
Economic environment	Why is Khadi not gaining momentum in the Indian economic condition?	Consumers not appreciating	41	41	1.9	25	Consumers not appreciating	12.97	168.53
		Consumers may consider it outdated	24	24					
		Not interested to buy	21	21					
		Khadi is not branding itself	14	14					
	Do you think purchasing Indian products will increase the national income?	Strongly agree	21	21	0.65	30	Agree	18.55	344.24
		Agree	61	61					
		Neutral	13	13					
		Disagree	4	4					
		Strongly disagree	1	1					
	Do you think purchasing Khadi will boost domestic synergy?	Strongly agree	20	20	1.2	25	Agree	16.37	267.84
		Agree	60	60					
		Neutral	17	17					
		Disagree	3	3					
Strongly disagree		0	0						
By using Khadi products, is it useful to avoid unemployment in our country?	Agree	58	58	5.11	50	Agree	11.97	143.22	
	Disagree	42	42						

The table you provided presents data on various attitudes towards Indian culture, patriotism, the economic environment, and other aspects, using survey questions on Khadi and other cultural elements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Key demographic details about the respondents revealed by the analysis show that 46% of the respondents are in the 20-23 age range. 50% of responses are male and 50% are female, the gender distribution is balanced. In terms of marital status, 31% are married and 69% are single. Students comprise the largest occupation group at 47%, followed by those in business (18%), government (3%), private employment (25%) and other occupations (7%). According to the social class distribution, 77% of respondents say they are middle class, 15% say they are upper class and 8% say they are lower middle class. Given that 49% of respondents have a graduate degree, it appears that many respondents have not prioritized continuing their education after graduation.

Inferential Statistics

Perceptions about Khadi cloth:

- Is Khadi cloth eco-friendly? A high majority (61%) of respondents thinks that Khadi cloth is ecofriendly with 31% strongly agreeing and 63% agreeing. A further 3% disagreed and 3% were neutral. This reflects strong perception of Khadi's eco-friendly properties due to its natural production methods, which do not use other harmful chemicals.
- How is the price of Khadi compared? Half (48%) find Khadi price fair, 42% consider it costly. It was considered cheap by only 8% and very costly by 2%. This implies that at least half of respondents find the pricing of Khadi laudable since it can be produced locally to save import duties.
- Do you prefer Khadi? As far as the preference for types of Khadi is concerned, 50 percent would prefer cotton Khadi because of its comfort and its suitability at all seasons. This clearly shows that the youth is in favour of cotton crop resulting in its vogue in the market.
- What is your choice of Khadi from the list? Respondents prefer the Desi outlet (35%) most, followed by Raymond's (30%) and Reid and Taylor (22%). It corroborates strongly with local brands in Shivamogga.
- When is the best time to use Khadi cloth? More than 57 per cent respondents said they enjoy wearing Khadi during hot weather as it is cool. This also implies that Khadi is appropriate and comfortable the perfect clothing for the season.
- Who do you think Khadi cloths will be used more by? As for user demographics, 56 percent of respondents say that females are more likely to use Khadi cloth than adult males, because there is a larger variety of designs for women.
- Are we exporting our products of Khadi to foreigners? Most respondents, 67 per cent, agree that foreigners are ready to buy Khadi products and 16 per cent strongly agree. This is a positive view of the Khadi appeal beyond the border of the nation. Inferential statistics to analyze overall understanding of Khadi among respondents, *chi square* test was conducted. The calculated the *chi square* statistic to be 0.0 and p value being 1.0.

In the context of the survey conducted on youth purchasing patterns regarding Khadi in Shivamogga, the *chi-square* test was applied to assess overall sentiments about Khadi cloth across several categorical responses (e.g., eco-friendliness, price comparison, brand preference).

Hypothesis (H1): There is No Significant Relationship in Responses Regarding Khadi Cloth

The use of the *chi-square* test in this situation yielded important information about how the young people of Shivamogga understood and perceived Khadi clothing. The findings demonstrated a strong, consistent opinion about Khadi's attractiveness and environmental friendliness, highlighting its importance in regional culture and market dynamics. To further promote Khadi, marketing plans and

efforts are informed by this statistical analysis, which makes sure that the messaging speaks to the values and preferences of young people.

Khadi as a fabric has a lot of potential to be woven into a brand of ecofriendly product elements if there could be a strategic focus on it. The crucial point is that consumers must learn and accept the Khadi understanding and start looking for domestic clothes. This shift in mindset of the consumers can greatly influence local economies and help preserve aims of the cultural heritage. Moreover, the government should introduce special initiatives to encourage people to buy online Khadi products making them more available to more people. Today in retail, e-commerce has become a key part of consumer purchasing (Bhatia, 2020) and this digital transformation is necessary. Similarly, producers must innovate by introducing new variety of Khadi in sync with the prevailing trend in fashion. Producers can appeal to young consumers who place value on style but are also more likely to associate sustainable products with women's chintz fashion (Sinha et al., 2020). Also, consumers should also know the importance of their purchase of Khadi in promoting economic development and get employment in the country through local artisans and communities. Compulsory use of the Khad for public national events like Independence day would serve to boost national pride and motivate need for Khadi use. It also means renewing the cultural identity but also confirms a fashion statement for the general public. In addition, by highlighting Khadi as eco-friendly characteristic and unique quality we might be able to distinguish it in a competitive environment; especially when there are many overtly green playing the same card. Through educational campaigns it also cultivates an idea that a true Indian would put priority on the buying of domestic goods and support local industries.

Managerial Implications

For businesses and marketers of Khadi, several strategic points emerge. Firstly, positioning Khadi as an affordable, eco-friendly alternative could increase its appeal, especially among younger, middle-class consumers who are environmentally conscious. Yarangumelioglu Derya and Gsler Didar, say marketing campaigns that highlight Khadi's patriotism and sustainability could resonate with this demographic. Additionally, expanding the variety of colors and designs, as well as making Khadi more fashionable, can attract a broader customer base, especially younger consumers seeking trendy clothing options. The high demand for cotton Khadi suggests a potential opportunity to focus on developing more cotton-based Khadi products to meet consumer preferences (Baba, 2004). Additionally, there is potential for targeted marketing towards women, as they represent a significant portion of Khadi users. Expanding the product line to include more designs and fashionable options tailored for women could increase sales. Retailers could also consider collaborations with influencers or designers to create seasonal collections that align with modern trends, attracting more fashion-conscious buyers.

Theoretical Implications

From a theoretical perspective, the study underscores the importance of cultural and environmental factors in influencing consumer behavior towards traditional products like Khadi. The findings align with the theory of planned behavior, where attitudes toward eco-friendliness and cultural pride influence purchase intentions. The notion of Khadi as a representation of national pride, as well as its sustainable attributes, serves as a unique selling proposition (Modi, 2017). This study contributes to the existing literature by highlighting how traditional products can gain relevance in modern consumer markets when positioned with the right value propositions.

CONCLUSION

Khadi is recognized as an eco-friendly and culturally significant fabric in India, but to remain relevant in the modern market, it must adapt and evolve. Recent studies indicate significant opportunities for businesses to engage younger, environmentally conscious consumers by enhancing the variety and

affordability of Khadi products. Research exploring consumer attitudes towards Charaka Khadi products reveals that young consumers generally hold a positive view of Khadi cloth. New varieties of Khadi should also be introduced by producers that gel with current fashion trends. Producers can attract younger consumers who prioritize style over and above sustainability by adapting Khadi to meet the requirements of modern tastes. On the other hand, consumers need to know that when they buy Khadi they create and support job generation in the country through economic development.

Government employees on such important days as Independence day and on other important days, wearing Khadi can help to bolster national pride and encourage its usage. Not only does this reinforce cultural identity but it also lays a precedent for the public. Additionally, highlighting Khadi's eco-friendly features and its uniqueness from a market flooded with similar looks will differentiate it making it attractive to this crowd of environmentally conscious consumers. Campaigns to further the idea that a true Indian should buy at least priority of these domestically produced items is one another idea that though can be cultivated with educational campaigns that further support the local industries. Use of Khadi products can encourage the use of Khadi products can play their role in mitigating unemployment as more demand can increase employment opportunities in traditional textile industries. For this reason, one of the policies that could be adopted is to impose use of Khadi dress for government employees and this would encourage further implementation. Srinivasan, proposes an advertisement and marketing effort to redress the periphery that currently holds that Khadi is out of vogue and to demonstrate its contemporary cool edge. The use of these strategies will enable Khadi to regain its place as a fashionable and culturally important option for the consumer. The study aimed to deepen the understanding of ethnocentrism in India by examining whether Indians exhibit ethnocentric tendencies, how educational levels impact these tendencies, if age groups show differences in ethnocentrism and whether gender influences these tendencies. Results indicated that ethnocentrism among Indians does not significantly correlate with age, gender or educational background. Overall, while Khadi's historical significance and eco-friendliness position it favourably within sustainable fashion, its future success will depend on effectively marketing its unique qualities to a new generation of consumers who value sustainability and cultural heritage.

REFERENCES

- Datta, D. B., & Sarkar, B. (2022). Consumer buying behaviour towards khadi fashion wear. *SEDME (Small Enterprises Development, Management & Extension Journal)*, 49(1), 58-72.
- Aronczyk, M. (2013). *Branding the nation: The global business of national identity*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Bizumic, B. (2020). Ethnocentrism. *Encyclopedia of Child Behavior and Development*. Springer International Publishing, pp. 607-608.
- Alam, A. S., Goenka, A., & Nandkeolyar, D. (2022). Sustainable clothing: Exploring the awareness, attitudes and purchase behavior of Indian consumers. *South Asian Journal of Management*, 29(5), 148-163.
- Bizumic, B. (2014). Who coined the concept of ethnocentrism? A brief report. *Journal of Social and Political Psychology*, 2(1), 3-10.
- Bar-Tal, D. (1990). Causes and consequences of delegitimization: Models of conflict and ethnocentrism. *Journal of Social Issues*, 46(1), 65-81.
- Bawa, A. (2004). Consumer ethnocentrism: CETSCALE validation and measurement of extent. *Vikalpa*, 29(3), 43-58.
- Carpenter, J. M., Moore, M., Alexander, N., & Doherty, A. M. (2013). Consumer demographics, ethnocentrism, cultural values and acculturation to the global consumer culture: A retail perspective. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 29(3-4), 271-291.
- Ranjbarian, B., Barari, M., & Zabihzade, K. (2011). Ethnocentrism among Iranian consumer with different consumption habits. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 3(3), 30.
- Bhattacharyya, R. (2011). Khadi: From national fabric to fashion statement. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 46(36), 59-66.

- Bansal, P., & Kaur, S. (2019). Fashioning sustainability: A study on eco-friendly apparel choices among youth. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*.
- Bhatia, R. (2020). E-commerce trends in the Indian textile industry. *International Journal of Business and Management*.
- Sinha, A., Das, A., & Chakraborty, A. (2020). Sustainable fashion and its influence on consumer behavior: An empirical study. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*.
- Baba, A. (2004). Consumer ethnocentrism: CETSCALE validation and measurement of extent. *Vikalpa*, 29(3), 43-58.
- Modi, S. (2017). Ethnocentric tendencies and its influence on consumer purchase intent. International Conference on Technology and Business Management.

Received: 08-Jun-2020, Manuscript No. AMSJ-24-410; **Editor assigned:** 11-Jun-2020, Pre QC No. AMSJ-24-410 (PQ); **Reviewed:** 25-Jun-2020, QC No. AMSJ-24-410; **Revised:** 02-Apr-2025, Manuscript No. AMSJ-24-410 (R); **Published:** 09-Apr-2025